

Information and Reaction Balance in Statistical Mechanics

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In a set of previous notes, we obtained equilibrium distributions through reaction balance for specific reactions i.e. for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. In this note, we argue that “information” plays a role in reaction balance as one utilizes the most uncertain situation namely that all reactions $e_i+e_j=e$ have the same probability as outcomes in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. We link this to a factorial scheme for reaction types. In addition, we consider more general cases such as the Bose-Einstein and others in order to show that one again chooses the most uncertain scenario in terms of reaction outcomes (not configurations) subject to physical reaction enhancements or restrictions. For example, for the BE case, one no longer has equal probabilities for each $e_i+e_j=e$ because there is a physical enhancement $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ becomes $f(e_1)[1+f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1+f(e_4)]$, but uncertainty with respect to the outcome of a colliding e_1 and e_2 is maximized subject to this constraint. In this note, we try to show that reaction balance inherently incorporates the idea of maximum uncertainty (or maximum reaction outcomes) subject to reaction enhancement/restriction constraints. Statistical mechanics usually starts with the idea of maximum uncertainty or number of arrangements whereas we argue one may start with the idea of reaction balance. The latter incorporates maximum uncertainty, not of physical arrangements, but of reaction outcomes in time.

Simple Information Theory

In the literature, one often sees “information” theory i.e. alphabetical letter arrangements applied to large numbers of letters in a string, because in this case, the number of appearances of letter x_i is almost $P(x_i)N$ where $P(x_i)$ is the probability for x_i and N the number of letters. In such a case, Stirling’s approximation is applied to the number of arrangements. It seems the ideas of information theory may be seen for small strings as long as one imposes the constraint: number of x_i occurrences = $P(x_i)N$. For example, consider two letters a and b and a string of four letters.

For the case of $P(a)=.5$ and $P(b)=.5$ one has: $aabb, bbaa, abab, baba, baab, abba$ which follows from: $M!/[m_1! m_2!] = 4!/(2!2!)=6$.

For the case of $P(a)=.25$ and $P(b)=.75$ one has: $abbb, babb, bbab, bbba$ which follows from: $M!/[m_1! m_2!] = 4!/(1! 3!)=4$.

Thus, for this two letter case, the less probable letter appears less frequently and one only needs information about its position. Thus, for the second case, there are only 4 pieces of information needed while for the case of $P(a)=.5$, one needs to know about 6 arrangements.

This is captured in the entropy, where the number of arrangements:

$$2^{\sum_{i=1}^n P(x_i)} \ln(2) \sum_{i=1}^n P(x_i) \quad ((1))$$

For $P(a)=.5$ Entropy = $2(.5) \ln(2) = 1$, while for $P(a)=.25$ one has Entropy approx = .8.

Thus, $P(a)=.5$ has a higher entropy (more uncertainty, more arrangements) than $P(a)=.25$

One may show that:

$(M/2)! (M/2)! < (M/2-n)! (M/2+n)!$ so the case $m_1=M/2$ maximizes the number of arrangements or uncertainty in the above.

Consider the general case of $M! / [m_1! m_2! m_3! \dots]$ ((2)) for m_i and M large. Then, maximizing ((2)) using Stirling's approximation and the constraint $\sum_{i=1}^n m_i = M$:

$$-\ln(m_i) + 1 + b = 0 \text{ or } m_i = \text{constant} \quad ((3))$$

If one uses two constraints: $\sum_{i=1}^n m_i = M$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n e_i m_i = E$ where e_i is a quantity (like energy) associated with each letter then: $m_i = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ maximizes ((2)) as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case and Reaction Balance

From the above one sees that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $m_i = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ maximizes $M! / [m_1! m_2! m_3! \dots]$ where m_i is the number of particles with energy e_i subject to a constraint on total energy and number of particles. One may inquire as to what the arrangements in ((2)) pertain? Typically in statistical mechanics, they are said to apply to configurations or spatial arrangements. In this note, we argue they apply to possible reaction outcomes.

Consider the case of a particle with energy e_1 colliding with one with e_2 . In terms of energy conservation, all $e_i + e_j = e$ final particles are possible. What is the case of maximum uncertainty? We argue that giving all $e_i + e_j$ final outcomes the same probability maximizes uncertainty.

Imagine this is not the case and let m_1 represent the number of $e_3 + e_4 = e$ outcomes, m_2 the number of $e_5 + e_6 = e$ outcomes etc. Then, the arrangement of reactions in time is given by:

$M! / [m_1! m_2! m_3! \dots]$ and it is already known that $m_1 = m_2 = m_3 = m_i = \text{constant}$ maximizes this result for the constraint $\sum_{i=1}^n m_i = M$. Thus, all outcomes such that $e_i + e_j = e$ have equal probability.

One may ask why one chooses such a viewpoint. We argue it allows one to analyze more complicated scenarios such as the Bose-Einstein and other generalized reactions which impose physical enhancements or restrictions on reactions.

The Bose-Einstein and Other General Cases

In previous notes, we argued that one may apply reaction balance to the Bose-Einstein case, for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$:

$$f(e_1) [1+f(e_2)] f(e_3) [1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1+f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1+f(e_2)] \quad ((4))$$

where $[1+f(e_i)]$ is the physical boson scattering enhancement for a boson to scatter into a state which already has $f(e_i)$ bosons. Where does "information" or uncertainty enter in this case? It is no longer the case that all outcome reactions $e_i+e_j=e$ have the same probability because of the physical boson enhancement. One may argue, it seems, that there is maximum uncertainty in the reaction outcomes subject to the $[1+f(e_i)]$ constraint. In particular:

$$\begin{aligned} P(e_1+e_2 \rightarrow e_3+e_4) &= f(e_1)f(e_2) [1+f(e_3)][1+f(e_4)] \\ P(e_1+e_2 \rightarrow e_5+e_6) &= f(e_1)f(e_2) [1+f(e_5)] [1+f(e_6)] \quad \text{etc} \quad ((5)) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if m_1 represents the number of e_3+e_4 outcome reactions, let:

$$a [1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)] n_i = m_1 \quad \text{where } a = m_1 / [1+f(e_3)][1+f(e_4)] \quad ((6))$$

The strategy is to see if n_i is constant by maximizing the number of arrangements of outcome reactions in time i.e.

$$\text{Ln} \{ M! / [a! \text{Product over } i (n_i [1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)] a)!] \} \quad \text{subject to}$$

Sum over i $n_i [1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)] a = M$ or using Stirlings' approximation:

$$d/d n_i \quad \ln \{ n_i^{n_i} \} + C n_i = 0 \quad \text{where } n_i = [1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)] a$$

Where C is a Lagrange multiplier. This leads to:

$$\ln(n_i) = -C - 1 \quad \text{or} \quad n_i [1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)] a = \text{constant}$$

Thus, the number of reactions for $e_i+e_j=e$ which maximizes arrangements in time (or uncertainty or maximum entropy) is:

$$n_i = \text{constant} / [1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)] \quad ((8))$$

No additional factors result from the maximization and one already knows about $[1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)]$. It is the physical boson enhancement.

Thus, the reaction balance probability $f(e_1)f(e_2) [1+f(e_i)][1+f(e_j)]$ is associated with the maximum uncertainty for the reaction outcome $e_i+e_j=e$ to occur subject to the boson enhancement constraint. Matching the forward and time reversed reaction probabilities, taking \ln of both sides and linking to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ yields the probability distribution.

In the above, one may use the more general form:

$\ln\{ M! / [\text{Product over } i (g(f(e_i)) g(f(e_j)) n_i!)]$ and find that the same ideas hold. Thus, we argue that reaction balance inherently maximizes uncertainty in reaction outcomes subject to any reaction enhancements or restrictions which may exist.

Alternate Approach

As described in a previous note, one may rewrite ((4)) as:

$$\{ f(e_1)/[1+f(e_1)] \} \{ f(e_2)/[1+f(e_2)] \} = \{ f(e_3)/[1+f(e_3)] \} \{ f(e_4)/[1+f(e_4)] \} \quad ((9))$$

Then $f(e_i) / [1+f(e_i)]$ becomes the independent reaction factor (measuring overall activity). One may take \ln of both sides of ((9)) and link to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ to obtain equilibrium distributions. Alternatively, one may treat $g(f(e_i))$ as a variable and ask what value of $g(f(e_i))$ would maximize reactions subject to $\sum e_i g(f(e_i)) = \text{constant}$. This yields $g(f(e_i)) = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$. For the Bose-Einstein case $g(f) = f/(1+f)$ and one obtains the BD distribution. More general forms of $g(f)$ may be chosen to yield other equilibrium distributions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to show that reaction balance, which yields the equilibrium probability distribution without use of entropy, factorials or partition functions, inherently represents maximum uncertainty not in configurations, but in the outcomes of each reaction e_1+e_2 subject to any physical reaction enhancement or restriction and energy conservation. For example, for the Bose-Einstein case, the physical enhancement of a boson scattering into a state which already has $f(e_i)$ bosons is $(f(e_i)+1)$. Thus, there is preference to scatter into states with a high $f(e_i)$, but no other preference.